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FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE WITH THE HELP OF SITUATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of the essence of the intercultural approach to foreign language education, it also considers the technology for the development of intercultural communicative competence, which consists of three stages, through the analysis of the heroes of classical Russian and English literature.

Keywords: intercultural approach, intercultural communicative competence, technology, literature analysis, comparison, native and foreign culture, foreign language education.

Foreign language education has become relevant in connection with the process of globalization, as well as in connection with the expansion of international cooperation with various English-speaking countries. The main language of international communication is English. In 2022, this subject will become a mandatory federal exam, along with mathematics, which indicates its undeniable importance. In this regard, in the world of the 21st century, interest in foreign language communication is increasing every day. The process of globalization has led to the expansion of the information space, interpersonal and intercultural contacts, as well as the relationship between social groups, social movements, scientific cooperation, trade, and tourism.

It is important to note that situational modeling is a kind of physical modeling that reproduces a relatively small number of activity factors necessary and sufficient to adequately reproduce a specific situation of managing an object in the HMS (man-machine system). It is carried out in the case when it is impossible to create a functional layout capable of reproducing all modes and operating conditions of the system[1].

In turn, intercultural communicative competence is the ability to achieve mutual understanding with representatives of different cultures, even with mediocre knowledge of foreign languages, based on knowledge, understanding and compliance with the universal rules and norms of behavior that make up international communication etiquette.

All this proves the need for other approaches to teaching such a school subject as a foreign language. In recent decades, there have been changes in the theory and practice of teaching associated with the intensification of the search for innovative approaches to teaching and learning the language.

At the same time, it is advisable to emphasize that a foreign language culture is assimilated, learned by a student in the process of communicative foreign language education. It is assimilated in the aspects of cognition, development, teaching and education. Foreign language culture includes all the experience and all the

knowledge that was obtained by the student during the entire period of study in their works they study the interaction of language and culture, and the main task in teaching a foreign language is the formation of a personality ready for intercultural interaction with representatives of other countries.

To begin with, let's consider the prerequisites that determined the emergence of an intercultural approach to foreign language education with the help of the genetic principle, any theory is based precisely on the historical understanding of the processes of its formation and development in order to substantiate modern scientific trends. One of the key theories is the dialogue of cultures, which is becoming an increasingly popular category of linguodidactics: this fact is due to the fact that around the 1980s, the communicative approach began to gradually develop into an intercultural direction in foreign language education[2].

The main characteristics and features of intercultural dialogue can be attributed to:

- humanistic, anthropocentric nature of interaction;
- empathy, tolerance;
- equivalence and equality of participants in the dialogue;
- pluralism and diversity of opinions, full freedom of opinions and judgments;
- unconditional and full acceptance, as well as understanding of another person;
- openness to other views and positions, the ability to accept and understand a different point of view.

The main principle of education within the intercultural approach is the mandatory study of foreign languages and cultures on a comparative basis, which contributes to the successful implementation of the dialogue of cultures. It is considered appropriate to compare native and other cultures in order to better understand not only native, but also foreign culture. Moreover, according to E. G. Tareva, one's own and foreign culture, being interdependent, determine the special content of foreign language education, designed to put

into practice the “dialogue of cultures” (the concept of “dialogue of cultures” was borrowed by linguodidactics from cultural studies and literary criticism and introduced by Bakhtin to denote communicative interaction persons belonging to different cultural communities), to make it the main component in the consciousness of the individual, in the process of knowing one's own and other cultural reality[3]. At the same time, both cultures influence the student outside the educational space as well.

At the same time, the teaching strategy provides for taking into account the interaction of contacting conceptual and linguistic systems of all participants in communication - representatives of two different linguistic communities.

Such parity interaction provides for the following sequence of actions:

- 1) acquaintance with the reality (fact) of a foreign culture,
- 2) transfer to native culture,
- 3) reassessment and understanding of the fact of native culture,
- 4) comprehension of the facts of another culture,
- 5) reassessment of a different culture,
- 6) the formation of ideas about the native culture.

At the same time, the student “embodies” culture (native and other) for himself, appropriating its products as personally significant, introducing them into his own unique space of value coordinates[4].

S.S. Kunanbayeva emphasizes the ambiguity of the single term "intercultural competence", which is understood as an object of formation in the field of teaching foreign languages. The term "intercultural competence" is also used in a broad sense - as the ability to manage intercultural communication in the field of cultural studies or intercultural communication, which refers to communication between representatives of different cultures. The theory and practice of teaching a foreign language have determined the renewal of targets in teaching a foreign language.

The updated target settings are manifested in the formation of the ICC as the ability for intercultural communication in a person, defined as a subject of intercultural communication. Intercultural and communicative competence is realized through a set of subcompetences: cognitive, communicative, linguocultural, sociocultural, conceptual and personality-centered. [5,106].

The purpose of the formation of intercultural competence is indicated by G.V. Elizarova as “achieving such a quality of a linguistic personality that will allow her to go beyond her own culture and acquire the qualities of a mediator of cultures without losing her own cultural identity”[6]. In this definition, the author makes it clear that a foreign language is a means of intercultural communication.

O. A. Leontovich distinguishes “three components of intercultural competence: linguistic, communicative and cultural competences. [7]. In the context of intercultural communication, "linguistic competence is aimed at choosing language means that correspond to the situation of communication" [7]. According to Le-

ontovich O.A. “cultural competence involves the understanding of background knowledge, values, psychological and social identity, characteristic of a given culture. The concept of cultural competence to a certain extent coincides with the concept of cultural literacy...» [7, p.32-33]. Combining together, they form a qualitatively new whole, which has its own characteristics, different from each of the components taken separately.

The problems of intercultural communicative competence are considered in their works (I.A. Zimnyaya, S.V. Mureeva, I.L. Pluzhnik, T.A. Tkachenko, T.V. Parfenova) [8].

I.A. Zimnyaya, I.L. Pluzhnik define intercultural communicative competence as an integral personal formation, including the following components:

- general cultural (awareness in the field of general cultural knowledge and value systems that exist in different countries);
- socio-cultural (possession of the skills of interpersonal verbal communication with representatives of another country, compliance with the relevant ethical and etiquette speech norms);
- linguo-sociocultural, involving knowledge of lexical and grammatical units inherent in the language of various countries, their correct use in the communicative process.

I. L. Pluzhnik gives a specific definition of the essence of intercultural communicative competence: “intercultural communicative competence is the functional ability to understand the views and opinions of representatives of another culture, correct their behavior, overcome conflicts in the communication process, recognize the right to exist of various values, norms of behavior, becomes the maximum in demand for the modern specialist. It creates the basis for professional mobility, preparation for rapidly changing living conditions, introduces a specialist to the standards of world achievements, increases the possibilities of professional self-realization based on communication and tolerance" [14]. In this definition, the author highlights the professional component of intercultural communicative competence, which affects the goal and process of training specialists in the field of intercultural communication.

I.L. Pluzhnik, taking into account the integrative nature of intercultural communicative competence, reveals its didactic content, which includes:

- motivation to expand professional experience;
- knowledge about the socio-cultural aspects of the moral and ethical standards of communication in the countries of the language being studied;
- about the norms, behavioral attitudes characteristic of a foreign cultural professional sphere;
- about various language means of expressing communicative strategies and tactics for the purpose of effective, conflict-free behavior;
- skills and abilities: building and recognizing culturally specific norms of statements of a professional nature;
- flexible variation of speech utterance in accordance with communication strategies; understanding and

producing a foreign language text of a professional profile;

- professionally significant personal and behavioral qualities: cultural polycentricity and impartiality; tolerance;

- emotions and feelings: respect for the values of another professional culture and increased commitment to worthy examples in their professional field; emotional responsiveness. [9].

The analysis of this approach allows us to conclude from the whole variety of studies in the field of intercultural communication that his studies most fully reflect the essence of the very concept of intercultural communicative competence.

It is worth emphasizing that the intercultural approach counters a number of negative factors that may arise as a result of mastering a foreign language and foreign culture: it contributes to their partial or complete leveling. Thus, the intercultural approach allows you to partially or completely get rid of stereotypical thinking, intrapersonal conflict, cultural syncretism (lack of differentiation in cultural phenomena), as well as cultural exaltation (enthusiastic acceptance of another's culture to the detriment of one's own). The intercultural approach in teaching foreign languages dictates the need for the formation of intercultural communicative competence (hereinafter ICC), which involves the formation of the ability to carry out intercultural communication, without losing one's own national and cultural "I". It should be noted that the process of learning a foreign culture does not mean simply learning facts and memorizing information of a country-specific nature. This process should not be a search for "strangeness" and "unusualness" in the way of life of native speakers of the language being studied. In order to prevent ethnocentrism and stereotyped judgments, it is considered appropriate to study the realities of another culture through the prism of one's own culture, as well as to compare non-linguistic phenomena.

Some scientists consider it as the ability of people to coexist without mutual discrimination in one multicultural society. Others - as the ability to join a foreign language culture, to become part of it, others - as a factor that unites patterns of behavior in a certain situation[10]. However, almost all researchers are unanimous that the methodological concept of "intercultural communicative competence" implies, firstly, the availability of knowledge and skills that allow a person to successfully and effectively contact and interact with representatives of a different culture, and secondly, to effectively carry out an act of communication and thirdly, to participate in the dialogue of cultures: through the prism of a foreign culture, the student learns his national culture more deeply, which allows him to actively and effectively participate not only in a multicultural dialogue, but also in a dialogue with representatives of his society.

In conclusion, one can say after analyzing various definitions of this methodological term, we substantiated our working definition: ICC is the willingness and ability to communicate in foreign languages with representatives of other cultures, taking into account na-

tional characteristics, possession of background and sociocultural knowledge, foreign cultural concepts, as well as a personal guideline for a deeper knowledge of one's own culture through the prism of foreign culture. It is this conscious and cognitive attitude to the native culture that makes it possible to become a participant in the dialogue of cultures.

We believe that the successful outcome of intercultural and multicultural dialogue directly depends on the ability to behave in a certain cultural environment, which implies: knowledge of the customs, national character of the people, their habits, preferences, as well as the language of non-verbal communication. We all know cases when a representative of a different culture involuntarily insulted a foreigner, because he had no idea what a certain gesture or sign means in their country. That is why the ICC has no common features with the foreign language communicative competence (ICC) of native speakers and can only be characteristic of a mediator of cultures. A cultural mediator is a secondary language person who learns a particular language as a foreign language and acts as an intermediary between two or more cultures.

The main task of the mediator is to establish contact between partners in foreign languages, to smooth and resolve conflicts. For the purpose of the most successful development of the ICC, it is considered expedient to develop a special technology. Matching Two Heroes Students choose one hero from British literature and one from classical literature. Moreover, it is necessary to choose those heroes who are as similar as possible to each other in character (for example, Natasha Rostova from the novel "War and Peace"). Students analyze literary works, looking for those parts where a detailed description of the characters and actions of the characters is presented. Students work with a book and pencil, highlighting the places where you can find a detailed description of the character and actions of the characters.

Also, this technology can be used in a higher educational institution with students of a language university (bachelor's, specialist's, master's) in the study of such disciplines as speech practice and intercultural communication workshop. This technology will allow them to learn their native culture at a deeper level, as well as significantly increase the level of ICC, as students will analyze foreign literature in detail.

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